

LITERARY ANALYSIS OF ULUGBEK HAMDAMOV’S WORKS IN UZBEK LITERATURE

Sarsenbaeva Zoya Jangabay kizi

PhD., D.Sc. Candidate, Termez state university

Republic of Uzbekistan

E-mail: zoe.sarsenbaeva@list.ru

Annotation: The article deals with the literary analysis of Ulugbek Hamdamov’s works in Uzbek literature. The author states his opinions about the stories and works written by the author, and describes symbolic and metaphorical image representing good deeds in some works. The author notes that Ulugbek Hamdam, through the tragic tone of his poems, appears to encourage people to remain composed in the face of life's hardships.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, artistic psychology, storytelling, aesthetic elements, images.

INTRODUCTION. Modern Uzbek storytelling is evolving with new artistic and aesthetic elements. These include a deeper exploration of the hero's psyche, new visual tools of artistic psychology, the creation of symbolic psychological imagery, and even the interpretation of artistic-romantic textile images born from the writer's imagination. Each sentence carries a world of thought, and understanding the essence of these symbols requires profound artistic insight. In the writer's story “Muslim”, the concept of faith in people is depicted from two different perspectives through the characters of Hasan and Husan, who are twins born to the same parents, growing up in the same environment. Through these characters, the author seems to offer a resolution for individuals struggling to find clear answers to questions about faith. Hasan, for instance, sees true faith in sincere prayer, setting aside anything that might detract from it, while Husan expresses his faith through good deeds. For example, when both were about to pray, a neighbor's child asked for help with a task. Husan

went to assist and returned late, while Hasan, prioritizing prayer, chose not to help, saying: *“Pray first, then help”*. It is thus unsurprising that the writer chose to use the following verses of Alisher Navoi as an epigraph. *“Kimki bir ko‘ngli buzug‘ning xotirin sho aylagay,*

Oncha borkim, Ka‘ba vayron bo‘lsa obod aylag‘ay”.

In addition to the characters Hasan and Husan, the story effectively employs symbolic elements like birds and trees to convey the central theme. The story opens with the line: *“I came home, and a bird could not leave the yard”* (*“Ko‘klam keldi-yu, hovlidan bir qushcha ketmas bo‘ldi”*) [1]. This bird, introduced at the beginning, stays with the protagonists until the end of the tale. The birds in the story are described as: *“They seem like hummingbirds, but strangely, they are none of them; though they resemble all, they are still different”*.

In our view, these mysterious birds symbolize happiness within the human heart. Through the image of the birds, the author seems to suggest that faith in a person's heart leads to happiness through good deeds. Indeed, Husan's constant acts of kindness bring him peace and contentment. On the other hand, Hasan prioritizes prayer but remains discontented with situations that interfere with his worship.

The tree in the story, in our opinion, serves as a symbolic and metaphorical image representing good deeds. Since Husan continuously does good for others, the birds remain by his side.

After hearing of their father's illness, Hasan and Husan return home. Once their father recovers, Husan is surprised to hear the birds chirping softly as he walks in the garden, their song blending with his feelings of joy. This illustrates that a person can only feel happiness and peace in their heart through good deeds. At one point, the mysterious birds, who are always circling the twins, behave strangely. This occurs when the twins attempt to rescue a man being pursued by boys their age. As Husan hesitates, he notices the birds' chirping and follows their lead. Hasan, however, heads towards the mosque, with the birds following him. After Husan helps the man, the twins enter the mosque, and a piece of plaster from the ceiling falls onto the foot of an elderly man recovering from an injury. This falling plaster symbolizes Hasan's

inner turmoil, caused by the birds' displeasure when he rushed to pray instead of helping someone in need. The injured twins are carried out of the mosque. While Hasan heads to the mosque, Husan takes the old man to the hospital. One of the birds follows Husan to the hospital, while the other follows Hasan, circling restlessly until it disappears into the sky. This symbolizes that when a person neglects their moral duties, happiness departs from them [8].

At the end of the story, as the birds vanish, apricot blossoms start to fall. The apricot tree and its blossoms are symbolic of pure and sincere faith. The story “Stone” also uses modern artistic imagery to reflect internal struggles and life's challenges. The narrative features symbolic images such as a stone, snake, fish, girl, elder, and sun. These symbols act as keys to philosophical reflections, revealing the story's artistry and deeper meaning. The tale begins with the protagonist searching for the source of his inner turmoil, asking a rhetorical question: *“As time passes, the depression in my heart deepens, hardens, and turns into something solid, like a stone”*. In this context, the stone symbolizes the suffering buried deep within the human heart. But why does the protagonist always feel this pain? What is the cause of his lingering sadness? The suffering becomes a protective layer for the hero.

LITERATURE REVIEW. As observed in all genres of our literature, poetry is also undergoing improvements and renewals in terms of form and content. This process is mainly manifested in the artistic interpretation of the issues of man and his destiny, relationship with the world. Various poetic forms and methods of expression are emerging in the artistic research of these issues. Poet Ulugbek Hamdam's poetry attracts literature lovers with its content, depth of thought, originality of artistic expression. No matter what subject is written in the poet's poetry, in all of them he succeeds in creating unique artistic findings that invite the reader to deep observation. Commenting on the nature of lyrics, Jamal Kamal gives the following definition: *“Lyrics appear when a person knows his personality, understands himself as a person, considers himself a person in the universe, and looks at the external, objective world through the windows of his personal world. A person compares his personality with the world, sometimes he opposes it, sometimes he notes that he is connected and*

connected with the external world” [5, p.186-187]. In this sense, in Ulugbek Hamdam's poems, the virtues and vices that exist in human nature are expressed, the creator of humanity, the possessor of infinite perception, and at the same time, the owner of the ruthless power that creates the literal reflection of these qualities is artistic. is researched.

DISCUSSION. Various aspects of modern Uzbek poetry, including artistic psychology, the relationship between imagery and rhythm, methods of poetic interpretation of life, artistic characteristics, the personality of the creator and the lyrical hero, folk poetic thinking, methodological research, and the poetics of contemporary poetry, have been explored in our literary studies. In this context, particular recognition should be given to the work of Ulugbek Hamdam, a prolific figure in both literary studies and artistic creativity. It is well known that U. Hamdam's works have garnered public attention, and his prose has been the subject of numerous academic studies. However, his poetry has not been studied separately.

In fact, U. Hamdam is not only a distinguished literary scholar and talented prose writer but also a meticulous poet. His poems offer an artistic exploration of the relationship between individuals and society, covering a variety of themes and emotional states. Poems in the poet's collection “Old World and New Me” (“*Eski dunyo va yangi men*”) are divided into seasons called “Following Tradition” (“*An’anaga ergashib*”), “On the Road to Folk Melodies” (“*Xalq ohanglari yo’lida*”), and “Modernist Researches” (“*Modernistik izlanishlar*”). The collection also includes translations of the epic “New Man” (“*Yangi inson*”) and the works of Jalaluddin Rumi, Masset, Yevgeny Yevtushenko. In the poem “Moment” (“*Lahza*”) from the collection, the poet describes the importance and essence of a certain moment in a person's life as follows: *Shu lahza, bir lahza so‘ng lahza... Hammasini hal etib ketgay. O‘tmish, Bugun, Kelajak uning Quchoq‘ida murodga yetgay. Nechun dema, ey g‘ofil banda, Lahza –sening izmingda ot bir. Jilovini burasang qayga –O‘sha yerda bo‘lursan hozir!* [7, p. 70].

It seems that the poet turns to a unique form to express the artistic idea he wants to express and thereby achieves the density of the content. As noted by the scholar of

literature B. Sarimsakov, “All events, things and concepts in existence exist in the unity of content and form. Therefore, a certain thought, idea, event is realized and lives only through form. Because, just as there is no form without content, there is no content without form...” [6, p.92]. From the essence expressed in the poem, it can be understood that every moment spent in a person's life is a priceless blessing.

In Ulugbek Hamdam's lyrics, a number of poems expressing life, human life and its fate, glorifying its dignity were created through various poetic forms. In them, the poet demonstrated his creative originality in various themes and tones and created new aesthetic principles. In the poet's poetry, the balance of words, feelings, and spiritual experience constitutes a unique wholeness. The combination of poetic form and pictorial means in it gives the reader a clear picture to understand the existing reality and meaning: *Bu dunyonda do‘zaxni ko‘rdim, U dunyoda jannat bormikan? Tug‘ildim-u ayrildim, so‘rdim: Yorni qayta topmoq bormikan?..* [7, p. 89].

CONCLUSION. Thus, Ulugbek Hamdam's poems are unique due to the interpretation of universal problems, various artistic forms and methods of their artistic expression. The poet achieves artistic perfection in ensuring the balance of form and content in the details of the events of his rich poems. In the poet's poetry, a person's self-awareness, his virtues and vices, fate, in general, all complexity are artistically interpreted. It seems that Ulugbek Hamdam, through the tragic tone of his poems, urges people not to panic in front of the cruelty of life. After all, in life, a person constantly struggles with the vices of society and his own actions. He overcomes it with his fighting potential, sometimes he falls victim to it due to his own weakness.

References:

1. Hamdam U. Vatan haqida qo‘shiq –Toshkent. Akademnashr.: 2019.
2. Hamdamov U. Badiiy tafakkur tadriji. –T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2002.
3. Hamdamov U. Yangilanish ehtiyoji. –T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2006.
4. Кенжаева П. Хозирги ўзбек хикояларида қаҳрамон рухиятини тасвирлаш тамойиллари. ф.ф.н.дисс., –Т., 2008.

5. Jamol Kamol. She'r san'ati. –T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2018.
6. Sarimsoqov B. Badiiylik asoslari va mezonlari. –T., 2004.
7. Ulug‘bek Hamdam. Eski dunyo va yangi men. –T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2018.
8. Qizi D. U. M. ULUG ‘BEK HAMDAM HIKOYALARIDA MODERNCHA TASVIR //Konferensiyalar| Conferences. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 4. – С. 709-712.
9. Сарсенбаева З. Modernism in Uzbek literature and interpretation of images //Зарубежная лингвистика и лингводидактика. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 193-199.
10. Sarsenbaeva Z. A SYSTEMATIC COMPARISON OF SELECTED TEXTS BY D. MITCHELL //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
11. Sarsenbaeva Z. DESCRIPTIONS OF IMAGERY, SYMBOLISM, AND NON-REALISTIC ELEMENTS //Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit. – 2024. – С. 409-414.
12. Sarsenbaeva Z., Sarsenbaeva R. ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY IN TRANSLATION //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
13. kizi Sarsenbaeva Z. J. LINGUISTIC DIFFERENCES CONTRIBUTE TO VARYING INTERPRETATIONS OF SYMBOLS IN NON-REALISTIC WORKS.
14. Xamdamov U. XX asr o‘zbek she’riyati badiiy tafakkur tadrijining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari. Filologiya fanlarni doktori dissertatsiyasi (DSc) avtoreferati. –T., 2017.